

Design of drug delivery properties of biopolymers on inorganic materials

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Body of abstract

The computational modelling of drug delivery properties of biopolymers under real conditions is performed using multi-scale modelling to describe most efficiently the chemistry and biochemistry of complex processes. For instance, multiscale modelling of the molecular interactions at the bio-nano interface in biological cell membranes is inevitable in the assessment of drug delivery materials. The modelling is improved stepwise by considering an increasing complexity in each level of the model where the ultimate goal is to ensure a realistic modelling of the bio-nano interface. Interface properties, such as the interaction energy between an inorganic material and a biomolecule in a solvent environment, significantly depend on the nanomaterial and the biomolecule as well as the size of the material and the solvent. Intermolecular interactions between the materials and DNA in water are studied on the atomistic and mesoscale and obtained by multi-scale modelling simulations. An interface database containing the computed interaction energies and ranking with respect to the strength of the interaction of the biopolymers at the inorganic surfaces is created. This work was funded through EU Horizon 2020 Programme, grant n0 814572 (NanoSolveIT) and n0 731032 (Nano Commons), and SFI grant n016/IA/4506.

References